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ЖУРНАЛ НЕВРОЛОГИИ И НЕЙРОХИРУРГИЧЕСКИХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

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ANNOTATSIYA

Maqolada migrenning hissiy va shaxsiyatning buzilishi, depressiya, tashvish va vahima hujumlari bilan bog'liqligini ko'rsatadigan ko'plab tadqiqotlar ma'lumotlari keltirilgan. O'chokli tarqalishi, klinik ko'rinishi va diagnostikasi bo'yicha zamonaviy ma'lumotlar keltirilgan. Hozirgi vaqtda dunyoning aksariyat rivojlangan mamlakatlarida sefalgiya diagnostikasi yagona standartlarga muvofiq amalga oshiriladi, ularning asosiy lari bosh og'rig'ining xalqaro tasnifi hisoblanadi. Ishda migrenning komorbidligi va klinik va psixologik xususiyatlariga katta e'tibor beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Kalit so'zlar: bosh og'rig'i, hujum, aurasiz migren, aurali migren, migren tarqalishi, bemorlar, bosh og'rig'i, sefalgiya, tashxis, komorbidlik muammosi, ruhiy kasalliklar, depressiya va tashvish

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СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ДИАГНОСТИЧЕСКИЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ БАЗИЛЯРНОГО МИГРЕНИ (ЛИТЕРАТУРНЫЙ ОБЗОР)

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье представлены данные многочисленных исследований, которые показали ассоциацию мигрени с эмоционально-личностными расстройствами, депрессией, тревогой и паническими атаками. Приведены современные данные о распространенности, клинических проявлениях и диагностике мигрени. В настоящее время диагностика цефалгии в большинстве развитых стран мира осуществляется по единым стандартам, основным среди которых является Международная классификация головной боли. В работе уделяется много внимания проблеме коморбидности и клинико-психологическим особенностям мигрени.

Ключевые слова: головная боль, атака, мигрень без ауры, мигрень с аурой, распространенность мигрени, пациенты, головная боль, цефалгия, диагностика, проблема коморбидности, психические расстройства, депрессия и тревога.

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MODERN DIAGNOSTIC STUDIES OF BASILAR MIGRAINE (LITERATURE REVIEW)

ANNOTATION

The article presents data from numerous studies that have shown the association of migraine with emotional and personality disorders, depression, anxiety and panic attacks. Current data on the prevalence, clinical manifestations and diagnosis of migraine are presented. Currently, the diagnosis of cephalgia in most developed countries of the world is carried out according to unified standards, the main among which is the International Classification of Headache. The paper pays much attention to the problem of comorbidity and clinical and psychological peculiarities of migraine.

Keywords: headache, attack, migraine without aura, migraine with aura, prevalence of migraine, patients, headache, cephalgia, diagnosis, the problem of comorbidity, psychiatric disorders, depression and anxiety.

Introduction. Migraine is one of the most widespread and socially significant diseases, special attention to which recently has been paid not only by neurologists, but also by therapists, cardiologists, family physicians, psychiatrists, and other specialists. Today, diagnosis and

treatment of migraine are carried out according to unified standards, the main among which is the International Classification of Headache (ICGB). This is an episodic form of headache (GB), which is manifested by intense unilateral attacks of GB and a different combination of

neurological, gastrointestinal and autonomic symptoms. More often, pulsating GB begins in the oculo-forehead and temporal region. The pain may extend to half of the head, usually accompanied by nausea or vomiting, light and sound phobia, drowsiness and lethargy after the end of the attack [1].

Migraine is not a fatal disease, but it significantly impairs the quality of life of patients, leads to serious direct and indirect economic losses, which determines its special pharmaco-economic and medical and social significance. The direct and indirect costs associated with migraine are comparable to those due to cardiovascular diseases [11].

High morbidity, maximum representation of migraine is traced in young and middle-aged, i.e., working age. Socio-economic consequences associated with a decrease in the quality of life of patients, difficulties in diagnosis and therapy determine the great interest in the problem of migraine [4]. A population-based study was conducted in 8 cities and 5 rural districts of Uzbekistan in 2019-2021. It was found that the prevalence of migraine during the year is 23.6%. This is significantly higher than in most countries of the world [6]. According to the Global Survey, migraine ranks sixth among specific causes of disability, first among neurological diseases in 2015. It is shown that migraine affects about one billion inhabitants of the planet [3,12]. Currently, active study of this disease continues, data are accumulating on the role of genetic factors in the chronicization of migraine, in the development of comorbid disorders and dependence on the use of analgesics. Migraine is believed to be a genetically determined neurovascular disease [1, 10]. Recently, a socially important medical problem - migraine comorbidity - has received a great deal of attention worldwide. The fact that migraine, being a separate nosologic form, is combined with other diseases that significantly impair social adaptation and quality of life in general, explains the growing interest in the problem of comorbidity [9]. Migraine is known to be associated with autonomic dysfunction, arterial hypotension, epilepsy, anxiety, depression, asthenia, sleep disorders, brain infarction, cholelithiasis, craniio-vertebral anomaly, tension headache, and pericranial muscle dysfunction [8]. Numerous clinical and population-based studies have revealed the relationship of migraine with a range of psychiatric disorders. Understanding the nature of these relationships is essential not only for optimizing diagnosis and treatment, but can also serve as a basis for studying the etiology and pathogenesis of each of these disorders [11]. The important role of psychiatric disorders, primarily depression, in the formation of poor quality of life in migraine patients has been shown [1,6]. It has been hypothesized that serotonergic mechanisms that underlie sleep disorders and depression may provoke the occurrence of sleep migraine [3]. The directions proposed by A.M. Vein related to the study of the course of this disease in patients of different sexes, as well as the clinical picture of concomitant disorders arising from various functional states of the brain, seem particularly promising from the point of view of understanding the pathophysiology of migraine and developing new approaches to its treatment.

A.M. Vein proposed the theory of "pa-roxysmal brain" in migraine and epilepsy, drew attention to some differences in the course of migraine in women and men, noted the clinical features of right- and left-sided attacks, wakefulness migraine and migraine occurring during night sleep [5]. The comorbidity of migraine and depression has been described in detail in both individual clinical and population-based studies. A number of population-based studies have found a higher prevalence of depressive spectrum disorders (2.2-4 times) in migraine patients compared to their prevalence in the population. A study of 457 individuals aged 27-28 years was also conducted to identify psychiatric diseases and migraine in them. It turned out that migraine was 2.2 times more common in those with major depression. This was the first study to show an association between major depression and migraine in a random sample [3,6]. This relationship was subsequently confirmed. In individuals with migraine and other headaches (cephalgia) aged 25-55 years, the prevalence of major depression in migraine was found to be 3.5 times higher than in the population, and this association was even higher in patients with migraine with aura (4.9 times) [2,7]. It is shown that any chronic pain is quite often combined with depression. It is established that depression, as a rule, sooner or later leads to the emergence of chronic pain syndrome of one or another localization. In

persons with chronic migraine it has been shown that emotional disorders, primarily depression, are among the main "chronizing" factors determining the transformation of episodic GB into chronic [2, 6]. Clinically, the negative impact of depression on migraine cephalgia can be manifested by a significant aggravation of the clinical picture - an increase in the duration of attacks and intensity of the pain phase, the emergence or aggravation of existing muscle tension, dyssomnia, as well as the emergence or intensification of pain during night sleep, aggravation of the course of the interictal period - the emergence of asthenia, apathy, psychovegetative and psychosomatic disorders. To identify the relationship of depression and anxiety with migraine and non-migraine headaches, a cross-sectional population study of 50,000 people (clinical objective examination and psychological testing) was conducted in 2003. Individuals with non-migraineous and migraineous GB were found to have a higher representation of depression and anxiety, the severity of which correlated with the frequency of cephalgia episodes [4,13]. The study of the presence of major depression in patients with migraine, possible migraine (absence of one migraine criterion according to ICGB) and in control subjects confirmed the special relationship between migraine and major depression. The prevalence of major depression was 28.1% in patients with migraine, 19.5% in possible migraine and 10.3% in controls. Other authors studied the relationship between three pain syndromes (arthritis, migraine, low back pain) and three psychiatric disorders (depression, panic attacks, generalized anxiety disorder) in 3,032 adults (25-74 years) in the United States [3,5]. Moreover, depression was diagnosed in 28.5% of patients with migraine, 2.8 times more often than in subjects without migraine (12.3%). The close relationship between migraine and depression is explained by common neurochemical, primarily serotonergic and noradrenergic mechanisms of these two phenomena. It has also been shown that depression facilitates sensory transmission of pain due to somatic focusing-an increased attention to the painful area. Depression determines the specific pain behavior of a patient with chronic GB and significantly limits the choice of pain coping strategies, of which catastrophizing is the most common [1]. As a result, patients begin to perceive pain as a condition that threatens their health or even life, which aggravates the course of the depressive state. Eventually, they lose faith in the possibility of overcoming the problem of pain, hope for a cure, view their future as bleak, hopeless, and in some cases completely give up the struggle [7]. Each person's reaction to pain is determined by such factors as individual and cultural peculiarities of personality, past experience, emotional state at the moment of pain impact and circumstances under which it occurs. Therefore, the same pain stimuli produce different sensations in different people in terms of character and severity. It has been shown that pain stimuli trigger mechanisms of three levels: physiological - stimulation of nociceptive receptors, activation of pain neuropeptides, behavioral - pain posture and facial expressions, special speech and motor activity, and personal - thoughts, feelings, emotions [2, 3, 6, 7]. The role of personality traits in the development and course of different pain syndromes has been repeatedly discussed in the literature. One example is the well-known description of the so-called "migraine personality", according to which persons with migraine are characterized by a number of psychological features: ambitiousness, egocentrism, tendency to demonstrative reactions, striving since childhood for recognition of others, aggressiveness. They are pedantic, executive, somewhat rigid, strictly follow the generally accepted norms of behavior [5].

In most cases, migraine attacks occur spontaneously, their occurrence is unpredictable, which forms in these patients a sense of apprehension, anxiety, fear and, accordingly, disrupts daily functioning. Migraine patients are characterized by a special sensitivity to the impact of stress factors, low stress-resistance, tendency to anxiety-depressive reactions, behavioral, emotional lability, psychasthenic manifestations [8]. It is also shown that migraine patients often have a high motivation for achievement: they set significant life goals and, as a rule, successfully achieve them. Due to this personality type, even patients with frequent and severe migraine attacks tend to maintain their social status and success in their profession [2, 4]. Many people believe that migraine is the lot of the great. Many prominent people who made a significant contribution to the development of civilization suffered from

this disease. It is reasonable to recall that famous political figures - Julius Caesar, Napoleon I, Karl Marx; famous composers - Ludwig van Beethoven, Richard Wagner, Frideric Chopin, Peter Tchaikovsky - suffered from migraine; writers - Anton Chekhov, Mikhail Bulgakov, Heinrich Heine, Virginia Woolf, Edgar Poe, Guy de Maupassant; scientists - Isaac Newton, Jean Calvin, Carl von Linnaeus, Blaise Pascal, Charles Darwin, Alfred Nobel, Friedrich Nietzsche, Sigmund Freud, Jean Martin Charcot; artists - Pablo Picasso and others. [2,12]. According to the cognitive-behavioral model, any pain is not just a sensation, but a complex of multimodal experiences. When studying pain syndromes, it is necessary not only to study their sensory mechanisms, but also to take into account cognitive, affective, and behavioral characteristics that determine pain tolerance, pain behavior, and the ability to cope with the pain problem [3, 7]. The focus is on different behaviors (passivity or avoidance) and cognitive processes (attitudes, hopes, expectations, etc.) that may not only maintain but also exacerbate the pain problem. For example, patients with chronic pain syndrome who are convinced of their own helplessness and have negative pessimistic expectations about their illness are unable to cope with pain and control themselves. This type of cognitive evaluation can not only "fix" the pain problem for a long time, but also lead to a passive lifestyle and serious psychosocial maladaptation. In addition, it has been proven that cognitive processes have a direct impact on the physiology of pain, cause activation of autonomic mechanisms.

Comorbidity of migraine with psychiatric disorders is actively studied in prospective longitudinal studies, a feature of which is the possibility of clarifying the directionality of these relationships. The relationship between migraine and depression was studied in a prospective observational study of 1007 individuals aged 21-30 years. It was shown that the risk of developing new cases of migraine was 3.1 times higher in patients with major depression, and new cases of major depression were detected 3.2 times more often in persons with migraine than in patients without migraine. A 2010 prospective population-based study also showed that among 1,343 individuals, cases of major depression were 3.1 times more common in patients with migraine [4,12]. In several prospective studies, the authors emphasize the bidirectional relationship between migraine and depression [7].

There is evidence of a 2.4-fold excess risk of major depression onset in patients with migraine, with a 2.8-fold higher risk of migraine debut with major depression. Somewhat later, these authors confirmed the results of their study. In a two-year longitudinal follow-up, they found that the presence of depression increased the risk of new migraine cases by 3.4 times, which was not the case for other types of severe headache. In addition, the risk of new cases of depression was significantly higher (5.8-fold) in patients with pre-existing migraine. Thus, this association has a bidirectional relationship, that is, each disorder increases the risk of subsequent development of the other. The risk of migraine debut in patients with existing depression ranges from 2.8 to 3.5 and, conversely, the risk of depression debut in patients with existing migraine ranges from 2.4 to 5.8 [11]. The comorbidity of migraine with anxiety disorders is also known. Patients with migraine have been found to have generalized anxiety disorder at 3.9 times higher rates than individuals without migraine, 9.1% and 2.5%, respectively [3,5]. Other authors have obtained even higher rates of this relationship. In their studies, they showed that generalized anxiety disorder and social phobias are 5.3 and 3.4 times more common in patients with migraine than in individuals

without migraine [6]. Some researchers have emphasized that the association of migraine with anxiety disorder is as strong as with depression. Many of them have shown that the prevalence of generalized anxiety disorder is 3.5-5.3 times and panic disorder 3.6-3.7 times higher in patients with migraine than in individuals without migrainous cephalgia. At the same time, it was noted that the prevalence of depression in patients with migraine was 2-2.7 times higher than in individuals without migraine. Many studies on the psychiatric comorbidity of migraine emphasize the importance of the coexistence of depression and anxiety in migraine patients [2]. These relationships have been studied in patients with anxiety-depressive disorders. In this work, groups of patients with isolated anxiety and depression and with their combination were compared. A twofold increase in migraine risk was obtained among patients with the presence of anxiety and depression compared to patients who suffer from isolated forms of these disorders [3]. Other researchers also conducted a similar analysis and showed that the combined effect of anxiety disorder and migraine multiplies the risk of major depression. While the incidence of new cases of major depression in migraine is 2.7 times higher than in individuals without migraine, the incidence of major depression in people with a combination of migraine and any form of anxiety disorder is already 22.8 times higher compared to the incidence of depression among patients with migraine alone or anxiety disorders alone [8].

A close relationship between migraine and panic attacks has also been found. Based on clinical observations on a large sample of migraine patients, a special form of the disease - panic migraine - has been described. It is characterized by the presence of so-called panic-associated symptoms during a migraine attack - a sense of fear of death, general weakness, lipothymia, polyuria, chill-like shivering, palpitations, diffuse hyperhidrosis, dyspnea (feeling of shortness of breath). These symptoms follow the onset of headache, and the pain itself in panic migraine is rated by patients as less intense. The prevalence of panic migraine among patients with panic attacks is about 10% [5].

One study presents a comparative analysis of migraine features in young and elderly patients. It was noted that stabilization of hormone levels and loss of reproductive function are not the main factors determining the course and cessation of migraine in older age. It has been shown that over the years there is a change in the typical migraine pattern in the form of a reduction in migraine attacks, a decrease in the intensity of the pain phase of an attack, the appearance of episodes of migraine aura without headache, a decrease in the frequency of such typical symptoms as unilateral localization of GB and vomiting, pulsating cephalgia [14]. The obtained results indicate that the main factors contributing to the chronicization of migraine in older and younger patients are emotional and personal disorders, primarily anxiety-depressive disorders and dyssomnia [2,10].

Conclusions: Thus, migraine is traditionally considered as a prognostically favorable condition. Meanwhile, this chronic disease with debut at a young age disrupts the usual life stereotype, affects work capacity and family relationships. The prevalence of migraine and its high level of comorbidity with depression, anxiety, asthenia, dyssomnia, panic attacks, obvious consequences for patients' quality of life and social relationships determine the relevance and practical significance of this problem and article.

Bibliography:

1. Alekseev V.V. Chronic headaches. Clinic, diagnosis, pathogenesis. Autoref. dis. ... doctors of medical sciences. M.: 2006. 41 p.
2. Amelin A.V., Ignatov Yu.D., Skoromets A.A., Sokolov A.Yu. Migraine. Pathogenesis, clinic, pharmacotherapy. M.: MEDpress-inform, 2011. 256 p.
3. Artemenko A.R. Chronic migraine: clinic, pathogenesis, treatment. Dis. ... doctors of medical sciences. M.: 2010. 205 p.
4. I.D. Stulin, N.L. Kunelskaya, M.V. Tardov, E.V. Baibakova, M.A. Chugunova, Z.O. Zaoeva, I.M. Tardova "Basilar migraine: clinical features and differential diagnosis" Journal of Neurology and Psychiatry, 2, 2014
5. Koreshkina M.I. Modern methods of neuroimaging and preventive treatment of migraine. A neurol and a psychiatrist 2011;111(9/2):25-31. 5.
6. Yadgarov I. S., Abdukodirova D.T., Abdukadirov U. T. "Chronic migraine. Clinical observation. Review: clinic and treatment." "Journal of Neurology and Neurosurgical Research" number 4, issue 1. pp. 42-45. 2020.
7. Yadgarov I. S., Abdukodirova D.T., Abdukadirov U. T. "Shzrthb - Shzrthb (Shzrthb)" Shzrthb 2021 yil Shzrthb 4.

8. Yadgarov I. S., Abdulkadirov U. T. "MIGRAINE" Monograph 2021.
9. Hiaoying Sai, Hiaolei Shi, Himeng Zhang, Aiwu Zhang, Minying Zheng wa yannan Fang "miyadan olingan neurotrophic omil gene polymorphism va migraine shrtasidagi Association: meta-taxlil" Bosch ogrigi va ogrik journal (2017).
10. G.R. Tabeeva, N.N.Yakhno "Migraine" 2011.
11. M. I. Kamalova, N.K.Khaidarov, Sh.E.Islamov, Pathomorphological Features of hemorrhagic brain strokes, Journal of Biomedicine and Practice 2020, Special issue, pp. 101-105
12. Khodjieva D.T., Khaydarova D.K. Diagnosis and treatment of posttraumatic epilepsy. Journal of Research in Health Science 1 (2) issue 2018.
13. Khodjieva D.T., Khaydarova D.K. Clinical features of vertical sight disorders in patients with parkinson's disease. Journal of Research in Health Science 1 (2) issue 2018
14. Khaydarova D.K., Mansurova N.A. Analysis of Motor Complications in Parkinson's Disease Phenotypes. Journal of Advances in Medicine and Medical Research. 25(5): 1-7, 2018;

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